

AI Crypto Analog Barter System

Countries like India faces huge monetary problems because they buy things that are rated in dollars using rupees and 80 rupees = 1 dollar. Such countries should have two separate monetary systems. One internal monetary system using AI Crypto Analog currency and another is Nation's International Currency. ACA makes it unhackable and unbreachable system. The entire ACA design for internal transactions in the nation is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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